

Script's instruction:

- Should search the input data (website with constitutions) for the bag-of-words indicated in this document
- Output should indicate, in a matrix form, how many times each term is found in the constitution of each country, as below

	Search Term 1	Search Term 2
Country #1	# of times found in constitution	
Country #2		
Country #3		

- If it is also possible to extract a text document with the search terms highlighted within the full text, or else an extract of just the sentences within which those search terms were found (country indicated), that would be helpful.

Input data to be searched:

- Database with constitutions, all translated in English
<https://www.constituteproject.org/>

Bag-of-words

Search terms need to be in the context of:

- Ecosystems (dictionary)
- Geographical features (e.g. mountains, rivers, wetlands, oceans, forests, grasslands -as already defined)
- Nature (dictionary)

Terms that are “signals” that a pluralistic value approach is evident in the constitution (**R1**):

- World view*
- Weltanschauung
- Valu*
- Pluralistic + Valu*
- Participat*
- Indigenous + Knowledge
- Endemic + Knowledge
- Autochthon* + Knowledge
- Traditional + Knowledge
- Local + Knowledge
- Integrat*
- Multicriteria
- Deliberative + Evaluat*
- Multiple Knowledge
- Noesis

- Multiple Evidence Base
- Holistic
- Trade-off
- Tradeoff
- Complex
- Social-ecological
- Human environmental
- Socio-ecological
- human-environmental
- Rights of river
- Rights of land
- Rights to nature
- Environmental right*
- Instrumental + Valu*
- Intrinsic + Valu*
- Relational + Valu*
- Ecological + Valu*
- Environment* + Valu*
- Economic* + Valu*
- Cultur* +valu*
- Sustainable + Use
- Sustainable+ management
- Benefit
- Benefit+sharing
- Customary
- Wonted